

Handwriting Differences Across Gender and Analysing Age – Related Variations

Rishika Gautam¹, Shailja Singh^{2*}, Renu Devi³, Darshitha D S⁴, Meghna Sharma⁵, Priyanka Soni⁶,

¹M.Sc Student, Nims School of Forensic Sciences, Nims University Rajasthan Jaipur-Delhi

Highway(NH-11C), Jaipur-303121, Rajasthan,India

^{2*}Assistant Professor, Nims School of Forensic Sciences, Nims University Rajasthan Jaipur-Delhi

Highway(NH-11C), Jaipur-303121, Rajasthan,India

^{3,5,6}Assistant Professor, Nims School of Forensic Sciences, Nims University Rajasthan Jaipur-Delhi

Highway(NH-11C), Jaipur-303121, Rajasthan,India

⁴Research Scholar, Nims School of Forensic Sciences, Nims University Rajasthan Jaipur-Delhi

Highway(NH-11C), Jaipur-303121, Rajasthan,India

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ABSTRACT

Handwriting is a highly valuable motor function that is affected by intellectual, neurological and behavioural factors. This study examined at 5 major features slant, letter size, pen pressure, spacing and tremors with the goal to examine variations in handwriting features across age and genders. Three age groups (5-20), (21-40) and (41 and above) with equal distribution of gender constituted of 150 samples. The findings show statistically significant gender-based differences in pen pressure ($p = 0.035$) and letter size ($p = 0.044$); further there had been significant age-related variations in tremors ($p = 0.015$) and letter size ($p < 0.001$). These outcomes confirm the utilization of handwriting in forensic identification and behavioural studies; by demonstrating that it can be adequate indication of age and gender.

KEYWORDS

Examining handwriting, Differences between genders, estimating age, Pressure of the pen, Shaking movements, Forensic science.

INTRODUCTION

Handwriting is a complicated brain process which act as a unique personality trait that is influenced by range of factors that is psychological or physical. Usually called “brain writing” the fine skill is an evidence of a synchronized motor functioning of brain. This complicated synchronization begins in the brains motor cortex wherein the desires of writing include the processing of language, control of the muscles and acquired movement pattern. The physical process of writing thus becomes practicable as the electrical signal travels through the brain network system and stimulate specific hand muscles. Every individual encounters this procedure across an extremely distinct manner which leading to specific and identifiable handwriting features that are impossible for the same person to rewrite it regardless of various situation. ⁽²⁾

Handwriting examination is a useful biometric tool that enables behavioural profiling,

documents authorization and an identity verification from a forensic aspect. Handwriting can be helpful due to the comparison with fingerprint or DNA can be affected by thoughts and actions along with biology. Handwriting characteristics like slant, pressure, rhythm, and letter formation may be affected by a range of factors variable such as level of stress, personality characteristics, state of mind and intellectual growth a great deal of tension, for instance could result in writing which is compressed or unbalanced while a person who see secure and confident might use fluid-controlled strokes. In forensic psychology wherein handwriting could provide suggestions regarding an accused person's state of mind or habit of behaviour, those small sign indicates may highly valuable. ⁽¹⁶⁾

The persons cultural heritage educational attainment and exposure to the environment all impact the uniqueness of that distinguish their handwriting and enable them to determine an extremely personalized writing style. ⁽¹⁹⁾ Minor variations in spacing, pressure and formation may distinguish among genuine and false documents giving handwriting a trustworthy psychological biometric in legal inquiries because of its uniqueness ⁽³⁾ in addition handwriting is considered more trustworthy for overtime verification of identity as it seems to be stay constant throughout a period of time, despite the presence of short changes brought caused due to medical condition, sentiment or tiredness.

Differences in handwriting across genders is vary by physical, social and cultural traits. Women have more concise, round, and neater handwriting due to finer motor control and social reinforcement; whereas male have more angular and bigger showing differences in their muscles and geographical processing. ^(3,9) This characteristic was observed under different handwriting features like slant, alignment, pressure and spacing.

Age – related handwriting changes occurred as brain speed and neuromotor accuracy improved and degrade with age. With a consequence of age-related psychological changes and neurological disorders, older people have tremors and non-uniform spacing as compared to younger people showing more fluent handwriting skills. Such changes are more severe by Parkinsons disease and other neurological condition; hence handwriting is an accurate representation of age-related decline. ^(20,9)

Forensic experts needed to be aware of these age and gender specific handwriting patterns especially with handling unidentified messages, questioned signatures and psychological profiling. In judicial and investigative scenarios, a thorough approach that involves these variables enhances the accuracy and reliability of handwriting analysis. ⁽²⁾

In the end, handwriting offers an extensive database of neural, behavioural and biometric data which goes beyond simple interactions. Integrating gender and age analysis into handwriting research improves it forensics utilizes as well as extending our understanding of human expressions. Utilizing technological advances and broad perspectives will assists handwriting analysis becoming more accurate and evidence based for identification and behavioural investigations as the technology expands.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In a study total 150 sample were collected. Handwriting sample are taken on A4 size paper participant wrote a paragraph. Sample were collected as equal gender age distribution.

Three groups were divided Group A age 5 to 20 total 50 sample 25 girl 25 boys; Group B age 21 to 40 yr 50 sample 25 female 25 male; Group C age 41 above total 50 sample 25 female and 50 males.

Coding system was used to get a mean value

- Slant: coding was done in three ways Forward-1; Backward-2; Moderate-3
- Size: Coding was done in 2 ways Uniform-2; non-uniform -1

- Pen Pressure: coding was done in 3 ways Light-1; Moderate-2; Heavy-3
- Space: coding was done in 2 ways Uniform-2; non-uniform -1
- Tremors: coding was done in 2 ways if Tremors present-2 if Tremors absent -1.

RESULT AND DISCUSION

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Handwriting Characteristics by Age Group and Gender (N = 150)

Age Group	Gender	Slant (Mean \pm SD)	Size of Letter (Mean \pm SD)	Pen Pressure (Mean \pm SD)	Spacing (Mean \pm SD)	Tremors (Mean \pm SD)
5–20 yrs	Female	1.52 \pm 0.71	1.80 \pm 0.41	1.48 \pm 0.51	1.28 \pm 0.46	1.20 \pm 0.41
	Male	1.56 \pm 0.75	1.64 \pm 0.50	1.64 \pm 0.51	1.20 \pm 0.41	1.20 \pm 0.41
21–40 yrs	Female	1.96 \pm 0.89	2.00 \pm 0.00	1.52 \pm 0.65	1.32 \pm 0.48	1.00 \pm 0.00
	Male	1.72 \pm 0.94	1.92 \pm 0.28	1.64 \pm 0.76	1.28 \pm 0.46	1.04 \pm 0.20
41+yrs	Female	1.52 \pm 0.65	2.00 \pm 0.00	1.32 \pm 0.56	1.20 \pm 0.41	1.20 \pm 0.41
	Male	1.96 \pm 0.84	1.92 \pm 0.28	1.84 \pm 0.80	1.28 \pm 0.46	1.16 \pm 0.37

Figure 1: Handwriting characteristics – Female

Figure 2: Handwriting characteristics – Male

Handwriting Characteristic	Chi-Square Value (χ^2)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	p-value	Significance (p < 0.05)
Slant	2.006	2	0.367	Not Significant
Size of Letter	4.040	1	0.044	Significant
Pen Pressure	6.693	2	0.035	Significant

Spacing	0.035	1	0.852	Not Significant
tremors	0.000	1	1.000	Not Significant

Figure 3 Chi-Square Test Results by Gender

Handwriting Characteristic	Chi-Square Value (χ^2)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	p-value	Significance
Slant	8.858	4	0.065	Not Significant
Size of Letter	18.182	2	< 0.001	Significant
Pen Pressure	8.519	4	0.074	Not Significant
Spacing	0.624	2	0.732	Not Significant
Tremors	8.423	2	0.015	Significant

Figure 4 Chi-Square Values: Age vs Handwriting Characteristics

The study shows a significant result between age and gender. Letter size ($p = 0.044$) and pen pressure ($p = 0.035$) shows male exert more pen pressure and females produce more concise writing. This finding matches earlier research showing women have more uniform writing; Adams and Simmons; Genna and Accardo^(14,22) slant, spacing, tremors indicates that these three characteristics are more specific and flexible and have no significant gender differences.

A significant result in tremors ($p = 0.015$) and letter size ($p < 0.001$) was observed in age. Younger writers (ages 5-20) have more inconsistency in letter size which was improved in adulthood (ages 21-40) and declined in older people (ages 41 and above), which was related to the observation made by Sharma B, Dhillon D⁽²⁾ and Gupta S, Kumar P.⁽²⁰⁾

Tremors were observed in two age groups that is Group A (younger people aged 5-20) and Group C (older people aged 41 and above). This result was emphasized by Lomurno E, Toffoli S⁽⁶⁾ Saini K, Kaur M⁽¹⁰⁾, who finds that older people show increased tremors and the impact of age & neurological health on handwriting.

CONCLUSION

The research comes to the outcomes that handwriting is not just only a way to communicate in writing. It additionally serves as a behavioural characteristic that reveals valuable psychological and cultural information related to the writer. By doing an analysis of five basic handwriting features: slant, size of letter, pen pressure, spacing, tremors. The research revealed that both age and gender have a significant impact on handwriting styles. more precisely the result revealed that while men exert more pen pressure as compared to female on the other hand female have more uniform letter size. In addition, tremors and variation in size of letter were observed more frequently in younger and older age whereas in adulthood there was no tremors and the size of letter was uniform reflecting that handwriting is an indicator of age-related decline in cognitive. Although slant and spacing were not significant when examined independently, their correlation with other features deems them essential for comprehensive analysis. The study emphasizes the beneficial uses of handwriting analysis in a number of fields such as education, forensic psychological examination, and health monitoring. Lastly this study establishes a foundation for the effective utilization of handwriting as a trustworthy biometric marker and supporting the forensic concept that every

person style of writing is specific. For better reliability future research should build on more diverse samples and digital technique.

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